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AUTHORS

Yusuf Demirtas

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1404-2351>

Aslihan Gozutok

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-8051-166X>

AFFILIATIONS

Department of Public Health
Faculty of Medicine, Ordu University
Ordu, Turkey

Piraziz District State Hospital
Giresun, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Each year, injuries at work cause the loss of over a third of a million lives globally, highlighting their significance as a major public health concern (Takala, 2019). The incidence of fatal occupational injuries appears to be influenced by several socio-economic factors (Gümüş & Gülsün, 2020; Richardson et al., 2024). The aim of this study was to determine the trends and determinants of the fatal occupational injury rate in Turkey between 2001 and 2022.

Materials and Methods: This study, employing a longitudinal ecological design, used data from the Social Security Institution (SGK) Statistical Yearbooks (2001–2022) to obtain the number of active insured individuals and deaths due to occupational accidents under the 4-1/a category. Fatal occupational injury rates (FOIR) per 100,000 individuals were calculated by dividing the number of deaths by the number of insured individuals. Following a literature review, eight relevant indicators (domestic general government health expenditure, unemployment, GDP growth, inflation, employment-to-population ratio, proportion of workers in the construction sector, human development index, and educational attainment) were chosen to assess the determinants of the FOIR. The association between the FOIR and the selected variables was determined using univariate and multivariate linear regression analysis. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Results: In Turkey, the number of actively insured workers was 6.1 million in 2001, with 1,002 occupational injury-related fatalities, whereas in 2022, the number of actively insured workers increased to 19.8 million, and occupational injury-related fatalities increased to 1,517. The fatal occupational injury rate decreased from 16.3 per 100,000 workers in 2001 to 7.6 per 100,000 workers in 2022, exhibiting a fluctuating trend over the study period. In the univariate analysis, a higher Human Development Index ($B = -36.73$, $R^2 = 0.503$, $p < 0.001$) and higher education levels ($B = -0.161$, $R^2 = 0.323$, $p = 0.011$) were associated with lower FOIR, while a higher proportion of workers in the construction sector ($B = +93.63$, $R^2 = 0.282$, $p < 0.001$) was associated with an increased FOIR. In the multivariate analysis, the Human Development Index (HDI) emerged as the sole significant determinant of FOIR.

Conclusion: Over the 22-year period, although the number of occupational fatalities increased, the FOIR decreased due to a larger increase in active workers. The strongest determinant of this decline was the HDI, a composite measure of life expectancy, education, and gross national income. This finding highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to reducing FOIR, extending beyond healthcare services to include education and economic development.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Occupational health, occupational accidents, fatal occupational injury rate, Türkiye

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Yusuf Demirtas

Department of Public Health, Faculty of Medicine

Ordu University, Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1404-2351>

yusufdemirtas@odu.edu.tr